

THE EFFECT OF NEUTRAL SALTS ON THE HYDROLYSIS OF MAGNESIUM SULPHATE

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The hydrolysis and the effect on the hydrolysis of magnesium sulphate in aqueous solution, by the neutral salts—sodium chloride, sodium iodide and potassium iodide have been studied potentiometrically at 25°, using quinhydrone electrode coupled with saturated calomel electrode.

The hydrolysis, as also the effect of neutral salts on the hydrolysis of different substances, in aqueous solutions, have been studied by various workers. O'Sullivan (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1925, 21, 319) used the quinhydrone electrode in the measurement of p_{H} values in solutions containing magnesium and other bivalent ions of metals namely copper, zinc, nickel, cobalt, iron and cadmium, in their sulphate solutions. He did not study the effect of neutral salts on the hydrolysis of these salts.

Poma and Albonico (*Atti Accad. Lincei*, 1915, 24, I, 747) found that neutral salts accelerated the rate and increased the degree of hydrolysis of methyl acetate.

The hydrolysis of salts of beryllium and aluminium, derived from strong acids has been investigated by Cupr (*Publ. Fac. Sci. Univ. Masaryk*, 1931, 133, 3) using the quinhydrone electrode. The influence of neutral salts on the hydrolysis of beryllium chloride and beryllium bromide was ascribed to hydration.

Friedman and Stokes (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 61, 118) employed an electrometric method, using quinhydrone electrode coupled with a calomel electrode, to determine the effect of neutral salts on the hydrolysis of copper sulphate in aqueous solution. They found that potassium nitrate, potassium chloride and sodium chloride increased the degree of hydrolysis of copper sulphate solution in the given order. Those which showed a decrease are in the order of sodium sulphate and potassium sulphate.

In the present investigation the quinhydrone electrode has been employed to determine the effect of sodium chloride, sodium iodide and potassium iodide on the hydrolysis of magnesium sulphate ($\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$) in aqueous solution.

EXPERIMENTAL

All salts used in this investigation were 'Analar' (B.D.H.) quality. In all operations freshly boiled distilled water was used.

The quinhydrone electrode (a piece of bright platinum foil dipping into the salt solution in which sufficient quantity of solid 'Analar' quinhydrone has been added to make the solution saturated at 25°) was coupled with a saturated calomel electrode, the liquid junction potentials being eliminated by using a saturated potassium chloride—agar-agar bridge for coupling the electrodes. The set-up was placed in a water-bath, the temperature of which was maintained at 25° by an electromagnetic relay in conjunction

with a thermo-regulator. It was allowed to attain the temperature of the thermostat before measurements were made. The measurements were repeated over intervals of two to five minutes, for a period of ten to twenty minutes, depending upon the constancy of the readings.

From the E.M.F. the p_H and then the hydrogen-ion concentration of the solution was calculated.

From the hydrogen-ion concentration of the solution, its degree of hydrolysis (x) was calculated from the formula $x=(H)/2M$ where (H) is the concentration of hydrogen ions in the solution resulting from the hydrolysis of the salt, and M is the molar concentration of the salt.

In the following tables, (V) denotes the molar dilution and E.M.F., the measured electromotive force in salts; (H) is the hydrogen-ion concentration in g. mols. per litre and $100x$ is the %hydrolysis calculated.

TABLE I

Magnesium sulphate

Added salt : None.

Dilution (V).	E.M.F.	p_H .	$[H] \times 10^6$.	%Hydrolysis ($100x$).
10	0.1570 volts			
	0.1570			
	0.1580	Av: 0.1575	4.869	1.352
20	0.1680			0.0068
	0.1680			
	0.1680	Av: 0.1680	4.870	2.138
40	0.1760			0.0214
	0.1770			
	0.1770	Av: 0.1767	4.523	2.999
80	0.1840			0.0500
	0.1840			
	0.1830	Av: 0.1837	4.404	3.945
160	0.1880			0.1878
	0.1890			
	0.1890	Av: 0.1887	4.319	4.797
320	0.1920			0.3888
	0.1920			
	0.1930	Av: 0.1923	4.258	5.521
640	0.1950			0.8834
	0.1960			
	0.1950	Av: 0.1953	4.209	6.180
1280	0.1980			1.9776
	0.1980			
	0.1970	Av: 0.1977	4.168	6.792

TABLE II
Magnesium sulphate
 Added salt : 0.25*M*-NaCl.
p_H.

Dilution (V).	E.M.F.		[H] × 10 ⁵ .	%Hydrolysis (100%).	
10	0.1600 volts 0.1600 0.1590	Av : 0.1597	4.811	1.545	0.0077
20	0.1710 0.1720 0.1720	Av : 0.1717	4.607	2.472	0.0247
40	0.1810 0.1810 0.1810	Av : 0.1810	4.450	3.548	0.0709
80	0.1860 0.1870 0.1870	Av : 0.1867	4.353	4.436	0.1774
160	0.1910 0.1910 0.1910	Av : 0.1910	4.281	5.236	0.4189
320	0.1950 0.1940 0.1940	Av : 0.1943	4.225	5.957	0.9531
640	0.1970 0.1960 0.1970	Av : 0.1967	4.184	6.546	2.0947
1280	0.1990 0.1990 0.1980	Av : 0.1987	4.161	7.063	4.5203

TABLE III
Magnesium sulphate
 Added salt : 0.25*M*-NaI.
p_H.

Dilution (V).	E.M.F.		[H] × 10 ⁵ .	%Hydrolysis (100%).	
10	0.1100 0.1100 0.1100	Av : 0.1100	5.651	0.2234	0.0011
20	0.1180 0.1180 0.1190	Av : 0.1183	5.610	0.3090	0.0081
40	0.1250 0.1250 0.1250	Av : 0.1250	5.397	0.4009	0.0080
80	0.1310 0.1310 0.1320	Av : 0.1313	5.291	0.5117	0.0205
160	0.1370 0.1370 0.1380	Av : 0.1373	5.189	0.6471	0.0518
320	0.1430 0.1430 0.1430	Av : 0.1430	5.093	0.8073	0.1292
640	0.1470 0.1470 0.1480	Av : 0.1473	5.002	0.9954	0.3185
1280	0.1460 0.1470 0.1470	Av : 0.1467	5.030	0.9333	0.6878

Varying amounts (0.25*M*, 0.50*M*, 0.75*M*, 1.00*M* and 1.50*M*) of sodium chloride, sodium iodide and potassium iodide were added to magnesium sulphate solution and their effect on the hydrolysis of the solution was studied. The results have been shown in Tables IV, V and VI.

TABLE IV

Magnesium sulphate

Dilution.	Molality of added NaCl								
	0.50 <i>M</i>		0.75 <i>M</i>		1.00 <i>M</i>		1.50 <i>M</i>		
	Av. E.M.F. (100x).		Av. E.M.F. (100x).		Av. E.M.F. (100x).		Av. E.M.F. (100x).		Av. E.M.F. (100x).
10	0.1653	0.0096	0.1697	0.0114	0.1743	0.0137	0.1837	0.0197	
20	0.1760	0.0292	0.1803	0.0346	0.1833	0.0388	0.1937	0.0582	
40	0.1853	0.0840	0.1883	0.0944	0.1927	0.1120	0.1997	0.1472	
80	0.1887	0.1919	0.1917	0.2203	0.1973	0.2680	0.2030	0.3358	
160	0.1925	0.4406	0.1947	0.4842	0.1993	0.5795	0.2047	0.7146	
320	0.1957	1.0050	0.1977	1.0893	0.2010	1.2364	0.2060	1.5036	
640	0.1983	2.2240	0.1997	2.3558	0.2023	2.9070	0.2070	3.1270	
1280	0.1997	4.7117	0.2010	4.9453	0.2027	5.2995	0.2077	6.4320	

TABLE V

Magnesium sulphate

Dilution.	Molality of added NaI								
	0.50 <i>M</i>		0.75 <i>M</i>		1.00 <i>M</i>		1.50 <i>M</i>		
	Av. E.M.F. (100x).		Av. E.M.F. (100x).		Av. E.M.F. (100x).		Av. E.M.F. (100x).		Av. E.M.F. (100x).
10	0.1030	0.0009	0.0867	0.0005	0.0803	0.0004	0.0590	0.0002	
20	0.1087	0.0021	0.0900	0.0010	0.0820	0.0008	0.0620	0.0003	
40	0.1133	0.0051	0.0930	0.0023	0.0837	0.0016	0.0643	0.0008	
80	0.1177	0.0121	0.0953	0.0050	0.0850	0.0034	0.0660	0.0016	
160	0.1213	0.0277	0.0970	0.0108	0.0863	0.0071	0.0670	0.0033	
320	0.1240	0.0617	0.0983	0.0227	0.0870	0.0146	0.0677	0.0068	
640	0.1253	0.1298	0.0993	0.0470	0.0873	0.0295	0.0683	0.0141	
1280	0.1237	0.2430	0.0983	0.0906	0.0867	0.0574	0.0673	0.0271	

TABLE VI

Magnesium sulphate

Dilution.	Molality of added KI										
	0.25 <i>M</i>		0.50 <i>M</i>		0.75 <i>M</i>		1.00 <i>M</i>		1.50 <i>M</i>		
	Av. E.M.F. (100x).		Av. E.M.F. (100x).		Av. E.M.F. (100x).		Av. E.M.F. (100x).		Av. E.M.F. (100x).		Av. E.M.F. (100x).
10	0.0897	0.0005	0.0777	0.0003	0.0637	0.0002	0.0460	0.0001	0.0223	0.0000	
20	0.0947	0.0012	0.0793	0.0007	0.0643	0.0004	0.0470	0.0002	0.0240	0.0000	
40	0.0970	0.0027	0.0800	0.0014	0.0647	0.0008	0.0480	0.0004	0.0243	0.0001	
80	0.0987	0.0057	0.0803	0.0028	0.0650	0.0020	0.0483	0.0008	0.0247	0.0003	
160	0.1000	0.0121	0.0800	0.0056	0.0653	0.0031	0.0487	0.0016	0.0250	0.0005	
320	0.1007	0.0248	0.0799	0.0107	0.0653	0.0063	0.0483	0.0034	0.0253	0.0013	
640	0.1003	0.0490	0.0783	0.0208	0.0640	0.0109	0.0480	0.0064	0.0253	0.0030	
1280	0.0987	0.0918	0.0777	0.0405	0.0613	0.0214	0.0473	0.0134	0.0230	0.0030	

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

FIG. 3

It is evident that the hydrolysis of magnesium sulphate in aqueous solution increases with dilution and is further enhanced on the addition of sodium chloride. But, it is suppressed by the addition of sodium iodide and potassium iodide, in the given order; the decrease being more and more marked with the increase in concentration of the added salt.

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